

Stock Market Investment with Computer Vision Using Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract

An artificial intelligence, with convolutional neural network (CNN), stock trading system has been built for a less human-involved investment decision-making process to prevent human emotions from jeopardizing the return on investment. The results show great improvement in comparison to those of the paper on which our research project based and average professional investors.

1 Introduction

Stock investment involves a great deal of information and data, so much that humans, for decades, have been trying to conduct myriad of research projects on this very topic. Plenty of insights, theories, and even technical indicators (known as the practical embodiment of the financial theories by many people) have been created and improved over the years, however, humans still have a strong tendency to become irrational when it comes to pecuniary matters. The irrationality is usually derived from some human nature, like greed and fear, and it is this kind of emotions that frequently cost humans a steep one in the return of investment.

Computer programs and models do not have such irrationality like humans and hence are widely used in this area to prevent humans from making impulsive decisions. For the past decades, methods like statistical analysis, programming trading, and machine learning have been popular and generating insights. On the other hand, deep learning methods, especially with computer vision techniques (e.g., CNN), is a novelty in this area, and that is the rationale behind this research project.

A stock market trading decision model has been built with convolutional neural network, using computer vision techniques to learn the pattern and traits of historical trading data and give suggestions pertaining to stock trading actions (i.e., buy, sell, and hold) to help humans invest better. In this research project, we take JPM as the investment target because:

1. JPM is a large-scale and relatively stable (unlikely to be susceptible to manipulation) stock in one of the most mature trading platforms.
2. In the research paper [1] to which we take reference, they specifically (and only) put detailed return of investment (with graphics) on JPM. Hence, it would be easier to visualize the comparison of their results to ours.

This research project is based on the idea of a research paper [1] and several modifications have been made according to the advice from some trading and financial professionals, including input data used, input data pre-processing, and model training parameter, etc. with an eye to obtaining better results.

The following structure and content of this technical report subsume:

1. **Methods & Results:** Detailed implementation on input data gathering & processing, model building, and financial & statistical results.
2. **Findings & Conclusions:** Comments on the traits and attributes found and performance of the current work of this research project.
3. **Future Work:** Plans on improving the model accuracy and generalization.
4. **References:** Sources of research materials, code libraries, etc.

2 Methods & Results

2.1 Input Data Gathering & Pre-processing

The input data used is derived from stock prices of each trading day, which is open information. In this research project, the stock data (raw data) is gathered through Yahoo Finance's python api – yfinance [2], which includes detailed information regarding historical stock trading.

After gathering the raw data, for each trading day (an entry of input data), 11 technical indicators are calculated within 11 different time-period (6-day period, 7-day period, all the way to 16-day period) to form a 11 x 11 matrix, which represents an image that serves as a piece of input data ready for CNN model training. In addition, the order of the 11 technical indicators is determined in accordance with their nature, e.g., indicators that oscillate in between a range are placed closer to one another, while indicators that are not bounded by a certain range are grouped closer.

In terms of data labelling, there are 3 classes, i.e., buy, sell, and hold. Classification for training data is done by taking reference to past data of 5 days and future data of 5 days (i.e., if classifying data on 1 of January 2002, then data on days from 2 to 6 of January 2002 and data on days from 27 to 31 of December 2001 will be taken). If the day to be classified has the highest closing price within this 11-day timeframe, it'll be marked as 'Sell'; If the opposite, it'll be marked as 'Buy'; And any other value in between the highest and the lowest will be classified as 'Hold'.

In addition to generating input data and output data labelling, more processing works have been done:

1. **Normalization:**
Standard Scaler was applied to the training data since some of the technical indicators are not bounded by a fixed range, hence normalizing by dividing the range of the value would not work for all technical indicators used.
2. **Class Weight Adjustment:**
There is a serious data imbalance problem with how the data is classified (i.e., with buy, sell, and hold) because, by nature, the transaction action of most of the trading days is 'Hold' (most investors don't trade a stock too frequently since the optimal selling or buying point wouldn't show up that frequently and there's also a steep commission for trading too frequently). The ratio of 'Hold' to 'Buy' to 'Sell' is approximately 90:5:5.

Several data augmentation/adjustment methods have been tried and are to no avail, such as sampling up 'Buy's and 'Sell's and sampling down 'Hold's to balance the class distribution. Eventually, the best method that works in this research project is

to adjust the weight of classes. With the weight of 'Buy's and 'Sell's being 45 times of that of 'Hold's, the best results are produced.

2.2 Model Building & Training

The convolutional neural network model is built using keras [3] and tensorflow [4], with 5 hidden layers (3 2D-convolutional layers with batch normalization, followed by 2 fully connected dense layer). The categorical cross entropy loss function is also used, with optimizer being Adam.

Six years of data were taken into a group for training and testing over a 13-year period (i.e., from 2007 to 2019). For example, if year 2009 is to be tested, then stock data from 2004 to 2008 will be used as training data and stock data in 2009 will be used for testing, and the result of each group will be recorded.

2.3 Results

There are 2 ways of evaluating the results – investment simulation and machine metrics evaluation.

For investment simulation, 1000000 dollars is initially invested into the market targeting JPM stocks, and the results of trading will be recorded throughout the 13-year period. In each simulation day, a trading action will be conducted according to the model's output. For example, if the output is 'Buy', the simulation program will try to buy shares of JPM stocks with all the cash available; if the output is 'Sell', the simulation program will try to sell all shares possessed; if the output is 'Hold', then no action will be taken. Note that, if the output is 'Buy' and the simulation program already has some shares on hand (meaning the available cash would be 0), then this action will be ignored. The same goes with 'Sell'. If the output is 'Sell' when there're 0 shares, this action will be ignored.

Eventually, at the end of each year, the total assets will be calculated (cash and/or shares * share price at the last day of the year) and recorded to generate a year-to-year return of investment report. In addition to a comparison to the referenced paper [1], comparisons to the optimal results (i.e., results expected if all output labels are 100% predicted) and the Buy-and-Hold strategy (i.e., buying a certain stock shares in the beginning of a year, taking no other transaction throughout the year, and selling the stock shares at the end of the year) are also made, in order to have a clearer idea of the performance of our model.

From the images and the chart below, our results (with around 7 times of return of investment) outperform those of the referenced paper [1] (with around 4 times of return of investment), and that our performance's average yearly return of investment is around 26%, which is way higher than the performance of average professional investors.

Image 1 – Results of our model have almost 7 times of Return of Investment from 2007 to 2012

Image 2 – Results shown in the referenced paper have almost 4 times of Return of Investment from 2007 to 2012

year	optimal_start	optimal_final	optimal_return	pred_start	pred_final	pred_return	bah_start	bah_final	bah_return
2007	1000000	1706544.251	71%	1000000	1199266.5	20%	1000000	876674.36	-12%
2008	1706544.25	4141455.967	143%	1199266.53	2197719.9	83%	876674.4	651461.54	-26%
2009	4141455.97	19775872.31	378%	2197719.9	4498116.5	105%	651461.5	978366.57	50%
2010	19775872.3	31813952.5	61%	4498116.49	4994582	11%	978366.6	993997.93	2%
2011	31813952.5	34971242.53	10%	4994582.01	6596899.9	32%	993997.9	808600.32	-19%
2012	34971242.5	46066438.55	32%	6596899.87	7959413.9	21%	808600.3	1081550.5	34%
2013	46066438.5	68349044.25	48%	7959413.9	9586970.8	20%	1081551	1427560.2	32%
2014	68349044.2	138260224.9	102%	9586970.79	10848241	13%	1427560	1484564.6	4%
2015	138260225	233539443.8	69%	10848241.5	11393145	5%	1484565	1556200.9	5%
2016	233539444	352340574.8	51%	11393145.4	13661946	20%	1556201	2286555.8	47%
2017	352340575	616685296.7	75%	13661946.1	13967421	2%	2286556	2962511.5	30%
2018	616685297	972978382.2	58%	13967421.4	14375324	3%	2962511	2812275	-5%
2019	972978382	2231375088	129%	14375323.9	16855463	17%	2812275	3963290.4	41%

Table 1 – Results of our model (pred in the chart) are about 4 time more profitable than Buy and Hold (bah in the chart), while optimal results have a 2000+ times return (optimal in the chart)

For machine learning metrics, typical metrics are used, such as recall, precision, and F1 scores are calculated throughout the whole 13-year period (same way as the referenced paper [1]) and recorded in a table. From the tables below, the results of the referenced paper [1] are slightly better than ours in general. However, our performance on the precision on the class ‘Hold’ is slightly better than theirs, which could possibly explain our greater return of investment in the simulation (with a better precision on ‘Hold’, our model is able to avoid false buying or selling points and thus generate higher profit).

Total Accuracy: 0.58			
	Hold	Buy	Sell
Recall	0.55	0.80	0.81
Precision	0.95	0.22	0.18
F1 Score	0.70	0.34	0.29

Table 2 – Mathematic and Statistical Results on Overall Stock Prediction in the Article

Total Accuracy: 0.49			
	Hold	Buy	Sell
Recall	0.46	0.86	0.79
Precision	0.96	0.16	0.13
F1 Score	0.61	0.26	0.21

Table 3 – Mathematic and Statistical Results on Overall Stock Prediction of Our Team

3 Findings & Conclusions

Generating better profit as our model is, there are some intriguing findings:

1. This prediction seems to be highly dependent on individual cases, meaning that different stock might need different implementation or methods to achieve better results. Some other stocks are also tested with the method, along with the same parameters, used in this research work, yet the results vary quite a lot (for some stocks, the prediction results are outperformed by the results of Buy-and-Hold strategy).
2. Due to the fluctuating (and at times periodical) nature of stock prices, it seems that it is almost impossible for any model to make predictions with accuracy close to 100%.

Below are some more explanations on point 2 mentioned above:

The mechanism behind the labelling is of relativity. An entry of data is labelled 'Buy' (or 'Sell') if the close price of that entry is the lowest (or highest) within a certain period. The idea of having the highest or lowest close price is based on comparison to both past and future close prices (and this is how the labelling in this project works). It seems that the model can discern an increasing or decreasing pattern (by comparison to past closing prices), however, the model currently is not able to spot the pinnacle or the lowest point. This is understandable because only when a trend of decrease starts can we know that the pinnacle has emerged and there's just no way to know if any current point is the highest point (and the same goes with the lowest price point). At the same time, when providing data for the model to predict, only current or past data would be available, hence, unless the model can learn a general and stable enough pattern from current and past data (which is the ultimate goal of the project, but now seems to be the very obstacle to precise prediction), the model can only make guesses on the highest or the lowest price point when it discern an increasing or decreasing pattern.

Image 3 – It's highly possible that model learns that when seeing an increasing (or decreasing) trend over a set of days, it is the right moment to sell (or buy). But, when the model is only fed with current and past data, along with the fact that there's no guarantee that each increasing (or decreasing) trend will last for the same number of days, the model will have a hard time knowing where the pinnacle or nadir is.

Hence, there are several consecutive predictions of 'Buy's and 'Sell's over a short period of time with an increasing or decreasing trend in stock price (meaning that the model notices a trend of increase or decrease, but does not know when the highest or lowest point would appear, so it makes guesses when getting close to the actual highest or lowest point), while those

predicted as ‘Buy’ and ‘Hold’ should actually be categorized as ‘Hold’. (Check images below, where 1 represents ‘Sell’, 2 represents ‘Buy’, and 0 represents ‘Hold’).

After reaching the actual highest or lowest point, which means the stock price would start to decrease or increase, the model stops making predictions of ‘Sell’ or ‘Buy’, because the model knows the highest point, or the lowest point has passed.

date	price	predicetd label	original label
2018-04-27	109.400002	2	0
2018-04-30	108.779999	2	0
2018-05-01	108.779999	2	0
2018-05-02	107.919998	2	0
2018-05-03	107.239998	2	2
2018-05-04	108.43	0	0

Image 4 - Consecutive prediction of ‘Buy’ during a trend of decrease in price, and the prediction of ‘Buy’ stopped after the close price started to increase

date	price	predicetd label	original label
2018-08-03	117.089996	1	0
2018-08-06	117.120003	1	0
2018-08-07	117.550003	1	0
2018-08-08	117.790001	1	1
2018-08-09	116.879997	0	0

Image 5 - Consecutive prediction of ‘Sell’ during a trend of increase in price, and the prediction of ‘Sell’ stopped after the close price started to decrease

This kind of prediction model seems not to be able to generalize to all stocks, hence, if prediction on multiple stocks (e.g., creating a portfolio), different model and more experiments will have to be implemented. In addition, it’s probably not possible to 100% (or close) predict the selling and buying point (i.e., the local highest and lowest point) with this kind of training method, and this actually echoes the reality in which stock markets represent the actions and thoughts of investors (i.e., humans that are easily susceptible to emotions and unpredictable).

4 Future Work

There are currently two main paths for future endeavor on the effort to maximize the profit:

1. Try applying more mathematic and advanced deep learning techniques to improve our model’s feature learning, in order to figure out a way to accurately predict the local highest and lowest point with only references to current and past data.
2. Try labelling data with attributes of a fixed or a more objective rule, such as ‘Closing Price Will Increase on the Next Day’ and ‘Closing Price Will Decrease on the Next Day’. The model would only produce objective predictions (predicting ‘Increasing’ or ‘Decreasing’ is objective, while predicting ‘Buy’, ‘Sell’, or ‘Hold’ is subjective), and the actual transaction action can be left for investors to decide.

5 References

- [1] Omer Berat Serez, Murat Ozbayoglu: [Algorithmic Financial Trading with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks: Time Series to Image Conversion Approach](#)
- [2] Yahoo Finance: <https://pypi.org/project/yfinance/>
- [3] keras: <https://keras.io>
- [4] tensorflow: <https://www.tensorflow.org>